

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ON WIDTHS OF SETS GENERATED BY ONE SECTORIAL OPERATOR

Koshkarova B.

*L.N. Gumilyov ENU, Department of Pure Mathematics
ass. professor, Candidate of Phys. and Math. Sc.*

Kussainova L.

*L.N. Gumilyov ENU, Department of Pure Mathematics
professor, Doctor of Phys. and Math. Sc.*

Abstract

The conditions for the existence of closed sectorial extension of the one form of anisotropic type and the estimates of linear widths of one compact sets generated by the operator L are obtained.

Keywords: Differential operator, Sectorial form, Set widths.

The first results on estimates of the widths of the Sobolev weight classes appeared in the 60-70 of the 20th century in the works of M.Sh. Birman and M.Z. Solomyak [3], A. El Kooli [6] and H. Triebel [12]. This problem has been intensively studied since the 1990.

For weights of general form, upper and lower bounds for the Kolmogorov and linear widths of the Sobolev weight classes in the weight space L_q were obtained by P.I. Lizorkin, M.O. Otelbaev [8], [9], M.S. Aitenova and L.K. Kussainova [1], [2]. Here, the definition of the Sobolev weight class also included a restriction on the function itself (and this condition was essentially used).

In the work of A.A. Vasilyeva [13] the order estimates for the widths of the weighted Sobolev classes on a domain with the John condition in a weighted Lebesgue space with weights that are a function of the distance to some h -subset of the boundary of the domain are obtained.

We consider a complex-valued function $q[u, f]$ defined for $u, f \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$

$$q[u, f] = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \rho_k(x) \mathcal{D}_k^{l_k} u \overline{\mathcal{D}_k^{l_k} f} dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \omega(x) u \bar{f} dx, \quad (1)$$

here $\rho_k > 0$ ($1 \leq k \leq n$) and $\omega(x) = \omega_0(x) + i\omega_1(x)$ are locally summable functions in \mathbb{R}^n , $\kappa = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{l_k} < 2$, $\mathcal{D}_k = \partial/\partial x_k$.

This function $q[u, f]$ is a sesquilinear form on $C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ because it is linear in u and semilinear in f [5].

Interest in the study of operators associated with sesquilinear forms is primarily due to the study of boundary value problems in a variational formulation in domains \mathbb{R}^n with a nonsmooth boundary. However, the operators associated with sesquilinear forms are of undoubted independent interest, and their spectral theory is currently being actively developed (see, for example, [10], [11], [4]).

As is known, a symmetric operator L generates a symmetric sesquilinear form $q[u, f]$ and the converse is also true. The theory of such operators is quite well developed and belongs to the classical.

In our case, the sesquilinear form is not symmetric. Therefore, the study of the operator associated with a given form requires a special approach in each case separately.

The problem of studying the existence of a closed extension \tilde{L} of the operator L associated with the form $q[u, f]$ is the problem of the existence of a closed extension $\tilde{q}[u, f]$ of the form $q[u, f]$, as well as its sectoriality.

Let $D(q) = C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$. At first we research a problem about sectoriality of the form $q[u, f]$.

Definition 1 [5]. The set $\Theta(q) = \{q[u, u], u \in D(q), \|u\|_2 = 1\}$, where $\|u\|_2 = \|u; L_2(\mathbb{R}^n)\|$, is called the numerical range of q .

Definition 2 [5]. The form $q[u, f]$ is called sectorial if exist a number $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ and an angle φ , $0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2$, such that

$$\Theta(q) \subset \{z: \operatorname{Re} z \geq \gamma, |\arg(z - \varphi)| \leq \varphi\}. \quad (2)$$

We denote

$$\|u\|_W = \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \rho_k(x) |\mathcal{D}_k^{l_k} u|^2 dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \omega_0(x) |u|^2 dx \right)^{1/2}. \quad (3)$$

Let the space $W_2^l(\bar{\rho}, \omega_0)$, $\bar{\rho}(x) = (\rho_1, \dots, \rho_n)$, $\bar{l}(x) = (l_1, \dots, l_n)$, is the completion of the class $C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ in the norm $\|\cdot\|_W$.

For the form in (1) the condition (2) is equivalent to the inequality

$$\left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \omega_1(x) |u|^2 dx \right| \leq (C_1 \|u\|_W)^2, u \in D(q) \quad (0 < C_1 < \infty). \quad (4)$$

Inequality (4) follows from the embedding

$$\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |\omega_1(x)| |u|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \leq C_1 \|u\|_W. \quad (5)$$

For the solution of problem (5) we will use the inequality of type

$$\left(\int_{P(x)} |u|^2 v(x) dx \right)^{1/2} \leq C_0 \mathcal{K}_0(x, h; \bar{\rho}, v) \|u\|_{W(P(x))} \quad (6)$$

on characteristic parallelepiped $P(x)$ and then Besicovitch-type cover $\{P(x^j), j \geq 1\}$ [7].

In (6) $\|u\|_{W(P(x))}$ is norm of type (3), where we take $P(x)$ instead of \mathbb{R}^n and

$$\mathcal{K}_0(x, h; \bar{\rho}, v) = h(x)^{1-\kappa} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \rho_k^{-1/l_k}(x) \int_{P(x)} v(x) dx \right)^{1/2},$$

v is a weight.

Now we introduce the definition of characteristic parallelepiped $P(x)$.

Let $\bar{a}(x) = (a_1(x), \dots, a_n(x))$, $a_k > 0$,

$$P_{\bar{a}}(x) = \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R}^n : |y_k - x_k| \leq \frac{a_k(x)}{2}, 1 \leq k \leq n \right\}.$$

We denote $P(x, h, \bar{\rho}) = P_{\bar{a}}(x)$ if $a_k(x) = \left(h \rho_k^{\frac{1}{2}}(x) \right)^{1/l_k}$,

$$M_{(\delta)}(x, h; \bar{\rho}, \omega_0) = h \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \rho_k^{-1}(x) \inf_{\{e\}_\delta} \int_{P(x, h, \bar{\rho}) \setminus e} \omega_0 dy \right)^{1/2},$$

where $0 < \delta < 1$, infimum is taken over all compact $e \subset P(x, h, \bar{\rho})$ for which Lebesgue measure $|e| \leq \delta |P(x, h, \bar{\rho})|$.

We say that positive function $h(x) > 0$ is a length-function related to the pair $(\bar{\rho}, \omega_0)$ if there exist δ , $0 < \delta < 1$, such that $M_{(\delta)}(x, h; \bar{\rho}, \omega_0) \geq 1$ ($x \in \mathbb{R}^n$).

We put $P(x) = P(x; h(x), \bar{\rho}(x))$.

The following result is obtained.

Theorem 1. Let $\kappa = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{l_k} < 2$. Let $h(x)$ be a length-function related to the pair $(\bar{\rho}, \omega_0)$ and:

1) $\exists b_1 > 1$ such that $b_1^{-1} \leq \rho_k(y)/\rho_k(x) \leq b_1$ for all $y \in P(x)$;

2) $\exists b_2 > 1$ such that $b_2^{-1} \leq \rho_k(y)/\rho_k(x) \leq b_2$ ($1 \leq k \leq n$) if $P(y) \cap P(x)$ is non empty;

$$3) K_1 = \sup_x h(x)^{1-\kappa} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \rho_k^{-1}(x) \int_{P(x)} |\omega_1(\zeta)| d\zeta \right)^{1/2} < \infty.$$

Then

$$a) \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |\omega_1(x)| |u|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \leq C_2 K_1 \|u\|_W;$$

b) there exist the sectorial close extension $\tilde{q}[\cdot, \cdot]$ of the form $q[\cdot, \cdot]$, $D(\tilde{q}) = W$.

By the first representation theorem (see [5]) there exist the sectorial closed operator L associated with form \tilde{q} :

$$(Lu, f) = \tilde{q}[u, f], u, f \in D(q).$$

Example. Let

$$\rho_k(x) = (1 + |x_k|)^{2l_k}, \omega_0(x) = (1 + |x|)^\vartheta, \vartheta > 2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{l_k}.$$

It is no difficult to see that $h(x) = (1 + |x|)^{-\vartheta/2}$ will be the a length-function related to the pair $(\bar{\rho}, \omega_0)$.

As $0 < h(x) < 1$ we can show that statements take place

$$\frac{1}{2} \leq \frac{1 + |y_j|}{1 + |x_j|} \leq \frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{n}} \leq \frac{1 + |y|}{1 + |x|} \leq 1 + \sqrt{n} \text{ if } y \in P(x),$$

$$P(x) = \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R}^n : |y_k - x_k| < (1 + |x_k|)(1 + |x|)^{\frac{\vartheta}{2l_k}}, 1 \leq k \leq n \right\}.$$

The next result is connected with a problem on the best linear approximation of solutions of the equation

$$Lu = f; f \in L_2. \quad (7)$$

From the following estimates

$$\|Lu\|_2 \geq |(Lu, u)| \geq \|u\|_W^2 \geq c_0^{-1} \|u\|_W$$

it follows the sets embedding

$$\mathcal{F} = \{u \in D(L): \|Lu\|_2 \leq 1\} \subset c_0 BW, BW = \{u: \|u\|_W \leq 1\},$$

$c_0 = c_0(n, \vartheta, \delta)$.

Let \mathcal{U}_k is a set of all continuous linear operators $A: L_2 \rightarrow L_2, L_2 = L_2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ of dimension $\leq k$ and with the domain $D(A) \supset \mathcal{F}$.

Definition 3 [9]. The number

$$\lambda_k(\mathcal{F}) = \lambda_k(\mathcal{F}; L_2) = \inf_{A \in \mathcal{U}_k} \left\{ \sup_{u \in \mathcal{F}} \|u - Au\|_2 \right\}$$

is called the linear k -width of \mathcal{F} .

Let

$$\mathcal{N}(\lambda; \mathcal{F}) = \sum_{\lambda_k(\mathcal{F}) > \lambda} 1$$

is a countable function of width $\lambda_k(\mathcal{F})$.

Theorem 2. *The following estimate*

$$\mathcal{N}(c\lambda; \mathcal{F}) \leq c\lambda^{-\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{l_k}} \int_{\Omega(\lambda)} \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + |y_j|)^{-1} dy,$$

where

$$\Omega(\lambda) = \{x: (1 + |x|)^{-\vartheta/2} > \lambda\},$$

$$c = c(n, \vartheta, \delta) > 1.$$

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